

**EXPLORING THE DYNAMICS OF PRINCIPAL-TEACHER
PLANNING AND LEADERSHIP STYLES FOR EFFECTIVE**

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Abstract: The study investigated the dynamics between principals and teachers planning and leadership styles in secondary school administration in Obio/Akpor Local Government area of Rivers State. The study was guided by two research questions, and two hypotheses. The population of the study was 24 Public Senior Secondary Schools, consisted of 24 Principals and 1280 teachers in Obio/Akpor. 384 respondents comprising of 21 principals and 363 teachers constituted the sample size for this study. Data was collected using a self-structured questionnaire titled “Principal and Teachers Strategies for Effective Administration of Secondary Schools Questionnaire (PTSEASSQ)” with a reliability index of 0.86. The research questions were analyzed using descriptive statistics, percentage, mean and standard deviation. The study revealed a high extent principals and teachers planning strategies (3.19 ± 0.192) and leadership style (3.18 ± 0.194) of teachers for effective administration were also an influenced to effective management of public secondary schools. Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) for Principals -teachers planning strategies and leadership style are .580 and .511. The findings further revealed positive moderate impact between principals and teachers planning strategies and leadership style. Conclusively, the dynamics between principals and teachers in a school setting play a crucial role in shaping the educational environment, influencing student outcomes, and determining the overall effectiveness of school management. The results revealed that planning and leadership styles play crucial roles in the successful management and administration of public secondary schools. The Government should invest in professional development programs that focus on enhancing planning skills and leadership competencies among principals and teachers

Keynotes: Dynamics, principals-teachers, planning strategies, transformative leadership styles, effective

Introduction

The dynamics of principals-teachers are multifaceted and deeply influence the overall functioning and success of a school. Transformative leadership style, open communication, collaboration, professional development, inclusive decision-making, conflict resolution, and a positive school culture are key components of healthy dynamics. By fostering these elements, schools can create an environment where both teachers and students thrive Reem (2016). Effective administration in secondary schools is crucial for ensuring high-quality

education and fostering an environment conducive to learning and growth. The relationship between principals and teachers plays a pivotal role in shaping the administrative landscape of schools. This study focuses on the planning and transformative leadership relationship strategies employed by principals-teachers for effective administration in secondary schools Nkwon (2016).

The success of a school largely depends on the synergy between its administrative leaders and teaching staff. Principals, as the heads of schools, are responsible for setting the vision, establishing policies, and ensuring smooth operations. Teachers, on the other hand, are tasked with implementing educational programs and directly interacting with students. The collaboration between these two groups is essential for effective planning, decision-making, and leadership, which in turn, impacts the overall performance of the school Okeniyi (2013). According to Muheeb (2014) stated that there are numerous secondary schools facing various administrative challenges. These challenges include resource allocation, staff motivation, curriculum implementation, and maintaining discipline. Effective planning and leadership strategies are needed to address these issues and improve the educational outcomes in this region.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the critical role of the principal-teacher relationship in school administration, there is limited research on how their collaborative planning and transformative leadership strategies influence the effectiveness of secondary schools in Obio/Akpor. Understanding these dynamics is essential for developing interventions that enhance administrative practices and, ultimately, student performance. The following research questions guided this study

- 1) To what extent do principal-teacher planning strategies influence the management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State?
- 2) To what extent do principal transformative leadership styles enhance the effective administration of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State?

Hypotheses

HO Principal-teacher planning strategies have no significant positive influence on the management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

HO Principal transformative leadership styles have no influence significantly to enhance the effective administration of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design, utilizing questionnaires titled Principals-Teachers Strategies for Effective Administration of Secondary Schools

Questionnaire (PTSEASSQ) as the primary data collection instrument. It consisted of Sections A and B. Section A dealt with demographic information of the respondents while Section B dealt with variables from the research questions which were used to elicit information on principals planning strategies, transformative leadership style. This design is chosen to facilitate the collection of data from a large sample within the target population, providing a comprehensive overview of the influence of principal-teacher planning strategies and transformative leadership styles on the management and administration of public secondary schools. A stratified random sampling technique was employed to select participants. This method ensures that subgroups within the population (principals and teachers) are adequately represented. The sample size was 384 respondents comprising 363 teachers and 21 principals representing 30% drawn from the population 24 principals and 1280 teachers of Secondary schools in Obio/Akpor using Simple random sampling technique. Data analysis was Mean, standard deviation for research questions and hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Presentation of data

Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Figure 1: The position and gender of the responsibility

Figure 1 presented distributions of principals and teachers by gender respondents. Out of the total percentage, 5.5% are principals, with 3.1% being female and 2.3% male. Teachers constitute a significantly larger proportion, 94.5%, with 52.1% female and 42.4% male. This data suggests a higher percentage of teachers compared to principals, with a female majority in both roles.

Figure 2: The work experiences of the respondents

The figure 2 showed the distribution of experience among educators, measured in years. It shows that 13.5% of the individuals have less than 10 years of experience, suggesting a smaller group of relatively newer professionals. The majority, 52.1%, have more than 10 years but less than 20 years of experience, indicating a seasoned workforce. Lastly, 34.9% possess over 20 years of experience, highlighting a significant presence of highly experienced staff, potentially holding senior or specialized positions. This spread suggests a diverse mix of experience levels within the educational teachers

Table 1: Summary of mean and standard deviation analysis to determine the extent Principals and teachers planning strategies influence effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State

S/N	Principals planning strategies	Mean	St.Dev	Decision
1	Principal planning strategies in a school system is a must for good quality service teaching and learning	2.98	0.195	High
2	principal planning strategies is one of the ways of managing staff for effective administration	3.56	0.364	Very high
3	Financial planning by principals helps him to manage school funds	3.68	0.375	Very high
4	planning for school career day / week in school system leads to good quality service delivery	2.53	0.029	High
5	Planning for in-service trainings for staff lead to high quality service offer	3.22	0.369	High
	Aggregate	3.19	0.192	High

*Mean: 1.0-2.0 = Very Low Extent; 2.1-2.49 = Low Extent; 2.5-2.99 = Moderate Extent; 3.0-3.49 = High Extent; and 3.5-4.0 = Very High Extent

Table 1 is a Summary of mean and standard deviation analysis to determine the extent Principals and teachers planning strategies influence effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State. The aggregate mean of 3.19 with a standard deviation of 0.192 indicates a high overall perception among participants that principals' planning strategies are crucial for effective management in public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State.

Table 2: Summary of mean and standard deviation analysis to determine the extent Transformative Leadership Style influence effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State

Transformative Leadership Style	Mean	St.Dev	Decision
6 Laissez-faire transformative leadership style helps the principal control the male teacher insensitivity	2.60	0.057	Moderate
7 participative transformative leadership style in school system reduces the realization of a plan	3.24	0.241	High
8 Autocratic transformative leadership style produces results that were hope for in a school system management	3.69	0.327	Very high
Aggregate	3.18	0.194	High

*Mean: 1.0-2.0 = Very Low Extent; 2.1-2.49 = Low Extent; 2.5-2.99 = Moderate Extent; 3.0-3.49 = High Extent; and 3.5-4.0 = Very High Extent

Table 2 Summarized the mean and standard deviation analysis to determine the extent Transformative Leadership Style influence effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State. the result revealed an aggregate mean of 3.18 and standard deviation of 0.194 suggest that diverse leadership styles, particularly autocratic, are perceived as highly effective in managing public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State.

Table 3: Summary of PPMC analysis to establish the extent Principals and teachers planning strategies significantly correlates with Effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State

		Effective management	Principals and teachers planning strategies
Effective management	Pearson	1	.580
	Correlation		
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	384	384
Principals and teachers planning strategies	Pearson	.580	1
	Correlation		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	384	384

*R² = 0.3364

In Table 3, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) of .580 between principals and teachers planning strategies and effective management in public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State, signifies a moderate positive correlation. This indicates that as the planning strategies of principals and teachers improve or increase, there is a corresponding moderate enhancement in the effective management of these schools. The significance value (Sig.) of .001, which is less than the standard threshold of .05, confirms that this correlation is statistically significant. Furthermore, the R² value of 0.3364 suggests that approximately 33.64% of the variance in effective management can be explained by the planning strategies employed by principals and teachers. This highlights the substantial impact of strategic planning on school management effectiveness.

Table 4: Summary of PPMC analysis to establish the extent transformative leadership style significantly correlates with Effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State

		Effective management	Transformative leadership style
Effective management	Pearson Correlation	1	.511
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
	N	384	384
leadership style	Pearson Correlation	.511	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	384	384

*R² = 0.2611

In **Table 4**, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) of .511 between transformative leadership style and effective management in public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State, indicates a moderate positive correlation. This suggests that variations in transformative leadership style are moderately associated with changes in the effectiveness of school management. The significance level (Sig.) of .002, well below the conventional alpha level of .05, confirms that this correlation is statistically significant. The R² value of 0.2611 implies that about 26.11% of the variance in the effectiveness of school management can be attributed to the transformative leadership style. This data underscores the importance of transformative leadership style as a contributing factor to the management success in educational settings

Discussion

Onuorah & Eziamaka (2021) who opined that male and female principals did not significantly differ in mean ratings on their planning strategies. The position and gender of the responsibility, Okoroma (2016) finding was also in line with this study. This study revealed that female principals are better achievers of school’s goals than the male counterparts Out of the total percentage, 5.5% are principals, with 3.1% being female and 2.3% male. Teachers constitute a significantly larger proportion, 94.5%, with 52.1% female and 42.4% male. This data suggests a higher percentage of teachers compared to principals, with a female majority in both roles...

Amadi & Udisi (2021) findings revealed good principals staff management strategies enhanced effective administration, improve in productivity. The work experiences of the respondents showed the distribution of

experience among educators, measured in years. It showed that 13.5% of the individuals have less than 10 years of experience, suggested smaller group of relatively newer professionals. The majority, 52.1%, have more than 10 years but less than 20 years of experience, indicating a seasoned workforce. Lastly, 34.9% possess over 20 years of experience, highlighting a significant presence of highly experienced teacher, potentially holding senior or specialized positions.

The first research questions which is to determine the extent Principals and teachers planning strategies influence effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State. The aggregate mean of 3.19 with a standard deviation of 0.192 indicates a high overall perception among participants that principals' planning strategies are crucial for effective management in public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State. There was positive moderate relationship between principals and teachers' planning strategies and effective school management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local

Government Area in Rivers State ($r = .580$). this result was in line with Kanyip and Ogon

(2022) who studied the relationship between principals' administrative roles and Teacher's job effectiveness in secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State Nigeria. The corresponding hypothesis was stated as Principal-teacher planning strategies have no significant positive influence on the management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. It was found that the relationship between principals and teachers' role of planning is positive and moderately significant ($r=.580$; $p<.01$) the null hypothesis that state have no significant influence between principals and teachers planning strategies couldn't be retained but the alternative accepted. This finding was confined in the study by new leaders for schools (2009) retrieved from www.nsms.org June 15th 2022) where it was seen that schools make breakthrough gains are led by principals who have carried out radically new rules for themselves and their responsibility for school-wide practical to drive home knowledge for teachers and students' effectiveness. The finding was at identity with Onuorah & Eziamaka (2021) who submitted that female and male principals' secondary schools in Akwa education zone applied planning strategies for school's improvement and for quality assurance to a high extent. The possible reason for this finding is because of differences closeness in their ratings while t-test was used to test the null hypotheses with 0.04 level of significance. Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) of .580 between principals and teachers planning strategies and effective management in public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor, Rivers State, signifies a moderate positive correlation. This indicated that as the planning strategies of principals and teachers improve or increase, there is a corresponding moderate enhancement in the effective management of these schools

The second research question to what extent do principal transformative leadership styles enhance the effective administration of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. The corresponding research hypothesis was Principal leadership styles have no influence significantly to enhance the effective administration of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. The study found that the relationship between principals and teachers transformative leadership style showed a positive and moderate correlations with effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State ($r = .511$). Onubuleze & Cletus (2023) finding revealed that principals' transformative leadership Style in management of school plant in secondary schools to a great extent. The possible reason for this finding is because the principals' experiences (Interaction with teachers) over the years and understands disciplinary problems and may have applied them using trial and error basis, now knows the most appropriate strategy for the planning in this contemporary time. Okolie et al, (2022) was also identical with the study. Egboka & Igbokwe (2021) adopted the same descriptive survey research design but the findings

revealed among others that principals' instructional transformative leadership competency for effective management of secondary school is poor. This study, Principals planning strategies, Summary of mean and standard deviation analyzed determined the extent Principals and teachers planning strategies influenced effective management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the relationship between principals and teachers in terms of planning and leadership is crucial for the effective administration of secondary schools. The findings of this study revealed that principal-teacher planning strategies have a positive and moderate impact on the management of public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State. This indicates that effective collaborative planning between principals and teachers contributes significantly to the efficient management of schools, fostering a conducive learning environment and promoting better organizational outcomes. Similarly, the study showed that the transformative leadership styles of principals have a positive and moderate impact on the effective administration of public secondary schools. This suggests that principals who employ inclusive, supportive, and visionary leadership styles are likely to enhance the overall administrative effectiveness of their schools, leading to improved educational quality and school performance.

Recommendation

- Regular planning meetings and workshops can be organized to facilitate joint strategy development and ensure that all stakeholders are involved in the decision-making process.
- The government should provide Professional development through Continuous professional development programs should be provided for both principals and teachers. These programs should focus on enhancing skills in strategic planning, transformative leadership, and effective school management techniques.

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